

HISTORY OF THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: this article covers the history of the system of training specialists of the industrial sector in Uzbekistan, the development process of the industrial sector in Uzbekistan, the main tasks and priorities of the development of the Republican industry in the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on priorities for the development of the industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2011 – 2015"

Keywords: industry, crafts, hom-material, production, specialist, system, frame.

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The Uzbek industry has also gone through a number of stages in the process of its development. First of all, such forms as home industry ("maternal belly industry"), then crafts, that is, domestic industry, cooperation, manufacturing, factory, have arisen. There are many types of crafts, namely pottery, carpentry, stonework, binoculars, carving, embroidery, tanning, weaving and needlework, blacksmithing, misery and jewellery, degreasing, richthagging, Zoroastrianism, dyeing, tunneling, etc. Craftsmanship ("domestic industry") broke away from agriculture in the Bronze Age. In the early centuries AD, a significant number of craft centers were established on the territory of present-day Uzbekistan. In the 9th–10th centuries, Khiva and Shosh on yarn, cloth, carpet, copper and iron, Fergana on making knives, Bukhara on making silk fabrics, glass products were known to the world. In the 12th and 13th centuries, with the decline of development and the emergence of the Timurid state, crafts again developed. Crafts were of particular importance in the production relations of cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, Tashkent, Shahrisabz. After the industrial upheaval in England in the 60s and 70s of the 18th century, the gradual transition from manufacturing to machined industry began in Uzbekistan. Industries with primary processing of raw materials (cotton ginning, silk weighing, wine, canning, oil mills) have emerged. By the end of the 19th century, about 30 types of crafts had developed in Uzbekistan. In the early 20th century, however, the bulk of the crafts were converted into artels, later factories and factories, and art objects workshops. In the 20th century, there was a huge change in the industry of Uzbekistan. If at the

beginning of the century 5-10 xili (cotton fiber, raw silk, vegetable oil, grape wine, brick, hook, etc.) were produced from the most important types of industrial products, hundreds to thousands of varieties were prepared by the end of the century. Industry is the main and leading branch of material production. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 15, 2010, PQ – 1442 "on priorities for the development of the industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2011-2015" cited the main tasks and priorities for the development of the industry of the Republic in 2011 - 2015. In this:

- development of clear, deep and comprehensively thorough long-term prospects for the development of industry, on the basis of diversification of the main branches of Economics, deepening the mentioned structural changes;

- changes in the world conjuncture of the development of the Republic's industry, increasing the competitiveness of industrial products, normative indicators in order to reduce the sustainability of compatriots;

- The role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the world Division of Labor is aimed at promoting priority sectors such as energy, oil and gas chemical, chemical, textile and light industries, non-ferrous metallurgy, mechanical engineering and automobile, Pharmaceuticals, improving structural changes in the industry, improving the quality and deep return of agricultural products, production of building materials, continuous production of building materials in the world market, ;

- large-scale modernization of industrial enterprises, technical vatechnological updating, equipping them with the most modern high-tech equipment, rapid implementation of modern scientific achievements and advanced technologies in industrial sectors, expansion of high-level training for industrial personnel;

- diversification of production, sustainable growth of export potential on the basis of deep and high-quality processing of domestic raw materials, the development of competitive industrial products for export, the increase of production, the expansion of markets for their sale, development;

- further development of domestic industrial cooperation and production, creation of conditions for the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship in industrial sectors, placement of industrial enterprises in all-cities of the country and on the basis of import substitution, production of products, creation of new jobs to ensure the growth of employment of hamdaaholi, further increase in the level of;

- continuous reduction in the cost of labor productivity, production costs, implementation of energy and resource-saving modern technologies, improvement of production organization, continuous increase in industrial production due to elimination of losses and unproductive spending;

- focused on the systematic implementation of international quality standards and technical regulations that ensure its relevance in the production of an industrial product in the foreign market. The emergence and development of industry is an increase in the number of workers, and leads to an increase in its position in society. Speaking about the avant-garde role of workers in the historical renewal of society in Independence, it can be said that only the working class can help to protect, strengthen and permanently ensure the unification, cohesion and independence of the working masses. This opinion is confirmed by the reality of Uzbekistan day by day. The worker of Uzbekistan is building the gross social product of the Republic, the main part of the national income, is actively involved in raising the socio-economic potential of the country to a high level.

In the image of the workers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in all the workers of the United States, the sentiments of conscious industrial worker and humanist, progressive fighter for a new life, resolving high standards and universal principles, values, are embodied as a whole.

One of the important laws of industrial development is the cultural-technical, spiritual-educational level of industrialists, the inexhaustible increase in production skills and experience.

The higher level of knowledge and skills, production and skills, cultural and educational level of the working people of Uzbekistan can also be seen in the work carried out on the higher level of development of the industry.

Industry is the material basis of the country's defense capabilities, an important factor in maintaining El-yurt-security and stability, and neighboring countries, an important sphere that ensures independence, cooperation and solidarity.

The role of industry in guaranteeing the defense of the state of Uzbekistan is invaluable. Industry is such a branch that the political, economic patriotic aspirations of all countries, their economic unification, find their expression in the description of economic integration. As a result, the opportunity arises to rationally use the natural, labor and financial resources of all health professionals, all the achievements of science fiction.

Industry, especially heavy industry, is the key to solving the problems of industrialization of the entire social production. For this reason, the work of rebuilding the material and technical basis of the society began with the development of the industry in general, in particular, its most important areas, under the leadership of the Uzbek people. Because these areas were considered the foundation of the economic power of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the management of the welfare of the people, which will continue to be the case. The highest type of social organization of Labor – small business with a high level of concentration and

entrepreneurship - the pioneers of organizing social production on the basis of financing-specialization, diversification, cooperatification and specialization also dominate the industry and give good results.

The great driving force that ensures the acceleration of socio-economic development – competition, that is, competition, the struggle of opponents-will also develop in the industry. Efforts and other labor traditions have arisen and are coming into existence in the field of industry, in order to increase its relevance on the basis of the use of advanced techniques and technologies, the creation of new types of materials, increasing labor productivity, raising the competitiveness of manufactured products to a high level, improving a number of other technical and economic indicators of production. The advantages of independence and the economic policy of the state further increase the leading position of the state. The fundamentals of reforms and finding their solution are initially carried out in the industrial sector and have a good effect.

Modernization and structural changes in the economy process, with a wide involvement of foreign and internalization in its important sectors, are achieved through technical and technological facetfinding. During the period 2017-2018, investments in public capital in the Republic of Uzbekistan increased almost 1.6 times. Its khajmi was 68423.9 billion in 2017, down from 107333.0 in 2018 (\$equivalent to \$ 13.3 billion). Us doll.) or an increase of 118.1% compared to 20178. If we observe the dynamics of investments in fixed capital by year, then in 2005 – 2.0 trillion. Som or 12.0% growth, in 2010 – 10.8 trillion. Som or 9.0% growth, in 2015 – 28.5 trillion. it should be noted that the highest rate in the current year was 18.1%, which amounted to an increase in the amount or 8.1%. Speaking about the historical development of industrial production and its main consequences, it should be noted that the development of "home industry" on the territory of present – day Uzbekistan began 12-15 thousand years ago-during the Mesolithic period. Very simple labor weapons and items were made during this period.

During the new Stone Age (Neolithic, beginning of the 5th millennium BC), rowing, weaving emerged. At the end of the Neolithic period, metal weapons began to be made. From archaeological finds it is known that at the end of the 3rd millennium m, the inhabitants who lived in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan knew how to make weapons from copper. The progress of the process of making labor weapons during the period of the slave system (mid-1st millennium BC, 5th century BC), the improvement of metalworking led to the rise of craftsmanship, increased turnover and trade. At the beginning of the feudalism regime (in the 6th-8th centuries), Fergana mined gold, copper, iron, lead in iLok, silver, gold, Flint in the city.

In the 9th century, Samarkand was famous for its quality paper and lamp glass, the Shosh region spread along with most of its products. During that time, leather, cloth, silk, wool, clothing were issued from Central Asia to Eastern Europe, China and other countries via The Great Silk Road. Due to the feudal fragmentation that occurred in the 10th-13th centuries, the height of the conflict between the tribe and the elites, there were no major changes in craftsmanship. In the 2nd half of the 14th century, Emir Temür seized power in Samarkand and founded a centralized state, which, as a result, paved a great way for the economic and social prosperity of the state. By the end of the 15th century, tensions in Movaraunnahr would undermine the economic base of the Timurid state and development stalled. The emergence of Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand khanates in the XVI-XVIII centuries had a positive effect on the development of the economy, including industrial production in Turkestan by the XIX century

crafts have developed wood and metal carving, patterning dishes, floral printing on fabrics, artistic decoration of weapons. In the second half of this century, the development of the industry, especially the spinning industry, accelerated in the territory of Uzbekistan. In the early 20th century, many cotton ginning, oil-and-oil mills were built and put into operation. In 1925-1926, power plants began to be built. The first hydroelectric power plant to be built near Tashkent was launched on May 1, 1926. The construction of thermal power plants began in Samarkand, Bukhara, Kokand, Termez and Asaka. The number of such power plants reached 30 in 1930. The growing energy base provided an opportunity to build several new industrial enterprises. Before World War II, more than 500 industrial enterprises were built here, including "Tashselmash", Tashkent textile combine, Chirchik electrochemical combine, Cuttackurgan oil plant, bekabad and Quvasoy cementworks. The production of oil and non-ferrous rare metals, the preparation of products of the construction industry has developed. The role of the fuel and energy complex in industrial development is special. It includes energy, oil and oil processing, gas and gas condensate, coal mining and a number of other smaller industries. This complex accounts for $\frac{1}{4}$ of industrial production. The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the 10 gas producing countries in the world. There are powerful thermal power plants and hydroelectric power plants. The energy sector is the basis of the national economy of the Republic, a solid foundation of the economy and science and technology sector. The total capacity of the energy system of Uzbekistan is 12.5 thousand. The MVt included 37 thermal and hydraulic power plants. They received Rs 53 crore annually. it is capable of generating more than kWh of electricity. The total length of power networks in all voltages of the Uzbek energy system is about 300 thousand km. ni organizes. 42.6 thousand of network

Transformers MVt.ga is equal to. Now about 47 thousand employees work in the Republican energy system.

A full set of construction, adjustment, repair and other organizations within the state shareholder company" Uzbekenergo " ensures reliable operation, consistent development of the energy system of Uzbekistan. In January-December 2018, the volume of production, transmission and distribution of electrical energy and steam supply and air conditioning system and gaseous fuel production and distribution in this industry network increased by 4.1% compared to the corresponding period last year. Mining industry and open-pit mining. The volume of products produced by the mining industry and open-pit enterprises in January-December 2018 is 36.9 trillion.the sum was or 16.1% of the total produced industrial output. By the type of products produced in the mining industry, it is possible to observe that Flint mining increased by 1.2 times compared to the corresponding period last year, gas condensate-by 9.9%, natural gas - by 6.1%, coal mining - by 3.4%, while Gravel - by 12.3% and oil production - by 8.2%.

Fuel industry. The fuel industry of the Republic is formed and developing on the basis of coal, oil, gas fields found and mined in the Earth's crust. More than 160 oil and gas fields have been opened in the Republic, 115 of which are located in the geological province of Bukhara and Khiva, 27 in the Fergana Valley, 10 in Surkhandarya, 7 in Ustyurt. Now 71 oil, gas and gas condensates, 3 coal fields are used. More than 50 oil, gas and gas condensate fields have been prepared for future deployment. The fuel industry forms the main network of the Republican fuel and energy complex and consists of all types of fuel extraction, natural gas purification and supply, oil products processing facilities. They are served in all branches of the national economy. Large enterprises of the fuel industry are located in Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya regions.

Conclusion: metal extraction from ore on the territory of present-day Uzbekistan has a history of more than 4-5 thousand years. In ancient times, various objects were made from copper. Later, metals in the ore were used to Melt, pour and heat tin, silver, gold, etc., the initial coins were minted. In the early Middle Ages, jewelry, misery, blacksmithing, degreasing, richtagery flourished in a number of regions in the Fergana, Zarafshan, Chirchik, Ohangaran valleys. Although non-ferrous metals such as zinc, antimony, margimush, bismuth, cobalt are not known, their alloys have been widely used. The only enterprise operating in the field of ferrous metallurgy is the Joint-Stock Production Association "Uzbekistan Metallurgical Combine" in Bekabad. It produces steel and steel rolling mills, steel saws in various Rotary houses, and steel pipes, as well as beautiful and unobtrusive mysterious vessels.

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